

STUDY OF THE TRADITIONAL ECONOMY OF THE POPULATION OF THE SOUTHERN REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The study of the material culture and lifestyle of the population of the southern oases of Uzbekistan is another important issue of ethnographic research. The territory of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions has long been a convenient place for people to live. The works created since the 20th century contain information about agriculture, animal husbandry, crafts and trade, which are the main occupations of the population living in the region. In the southern regions, a kind of economic symbiosis has been formed over the centuries, that is, the traditional direction in one of the farms filled two other farms, which contributed to the establishment of close ties between them.

Key words: Southern regions, territory, region, traditional way of life, agriculture, animal husbandry, crafts, trade, tribe, settled, steppe.

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ТРАДИЦИОННОГО ХОЗЯЙСТВА НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ЮЖНЫХ РЕГИОНОВ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация: Изучение материальной культуры и образа жизни населения южных оазисов Узбекистана является еще одним важным вопросом этнографических исследований. Территория Кашкадарьинской и Сурхандарьинской областей уже давно является удобным местом для проживания людей. В произведениях, созданных с 20-го века, содержится информация о сельском хозяйстве, животноводстве, ремеслах и торговле, которые являются основными занятиями населения, проживавшего в регионе.

В южных регионах на протяжении веков формировался своеобразный экономический симбиоз, то есть традиционное направление в одном из хозяйств заполняло два других хозяйства, что способствовало установлению тесных связей между ними.

Ключевые слова: Южные регионы, территория, регион, традиционный быт, земледелие, животноводство, ремесла, торговля, племя, оседлый, степь.

ЎЗБЕКИСТОННИНГ ЖАНУБИЙ ҲУДУДЛАРИ АҲОЛИСИНИНГ АНЪАНАВИЙ ХЎЖАЛИГИНИНГ ЎРГАНИЛИ МАСАЛАЛАРИ

Аннотация: Ўзбекистоннинг жанубий ҳисобланган Қашқадарё ва Сурхондарё вилоятлари қадимдан инсонлар яшаши учун қулай макон бўлган. XX асрдан бошлаб яратилган асарларда минтақада яшаган аҳолининг асосий машғулотлари бўлган деҳқончилик, чорвачилик, хунармандчилик ва савдо сотиқ ҳақида маълумотлар учрайди. Жанубий ҳудудларда асрлар давомида ўзига хос хўжалик симбиози таркиб топган, яъни хўжаликлардан биридаги анъанавий йўналиш иккита бошқа хўжаликни тўлдирган, улар ўртасида яқин алоқалар ўрнатилишига ёрдам берган.

Калит сўзлар: жанубий вилоятлар, ҳудуд, минтақа, анъанавий хўжалик, деҳқончилик, чорвачилик, хунармандчилик, савдо-сотиқ, қабила, ўтроқ, дашт.

A. Anarbaev, who studied the formation of the first irrigated agriculture in Uzbekistan, based on archeological and polygraphic studies, noted that agriculture, animal husbandry and crafts were formed in the south of Uzbekistan from the 6th millennium BC [1].

At the end of the 3rd millennium BC - at the beginning of the 2nd millennium BC, a new era begins in the socio-economic lifestyle of the tribes living in Central Asia. During these times, a new farming location appeared in the south of

Uzbekistan (in the Sopollitepa and Jarkoton settlements of Surkhondarya) in the form of pottery culture[2].

According to archaeologists, the transition of ancient herding tribes to agriculture is considered a truly revolutionary phenomenon, and they called it Neolithic, that is, the revolution of the New Stone Age. By the end of the 2nd millennium BC, traces of the culture of the Tozabogyob and Andronovolik[3] tribes were also found in the territories of the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oases of modern Uzbekistan[4].

The current territory of Uzbekistan is divided into three agricultural zones depending on its natural and geographical conditions: mountainous and sub-mountainous zone (20.5%), irrigated land zone (18.2%), and the rest is a zone consisting of endless steppe-pasture lands. But not all irrigated land is suitable for irrigation. Agricultural areas located between mountain ranges and sand dunes, on river banks, have been known since ancient times in Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oases [5]. Archaeological studies show that the inhabitants of the Kashkadarya oasis have been engaged in irrigated and dry farming since ancient times [6].

Academician K. According to Shaniozov, the southwestern border of Shi region was close to the present-day Karshi regions. In some periods, probably until the middle of the VI-VII centuries, the present Karshi oasis was also part of the Shi region. In the Chinese chronicles, it is noted that the lands occupied by Nashebo (small Shi) belonged to the former Tuxolo (Toharistan).

In fact, the Nashebo region was in the hands of the Kushans, who ruled Tokhariston, until the 1st-5th centuries AD. Finally, the region of Shi became stronger and at the end of the 6th century they subjugated the region of Nasaf. His governors had the title of jabgu (jabghu) and were from the clans of governors of Kan (Samarkand region). The main part of the population lived in a sedentary position and engaged in agriculture. Customs and customs were more similar to the people of Kan. This situation indicates that the ethnoculture of the inhabitants of the Kashkadarya oasis and the Zarafshan valley is very close to each other [7].

The natural-geographical location and climate of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oasis have sharply different aspects in agriculture compared to other regions of Uzbekistan.

The analysis of the literature shows that the traditional economy and way of life of the inhabitants of the southern oases were closely connected with the way of life of other peoples of Central Asia. The natural-geographic location of the region indicates that agriculture and animal husbandry have been developed here since ancient times.

Historian and scientist P. Ravshanov, archaeologists who searched for traces of ancient life in the lower foothills of Kashkadarya did not come across ceramics at any location. However, noting that a special type of bow and arrow was found in these places, he says that these long-range samples indicate that the ancient inhabitants were mainly engaged in hunting. According to the scientist, the inhabitants of this area gradually moved from hunting to animal husbandry and living in a mobile way. Then, a sedentary life also begins to form as one of the unique manifestations of the lifestyle. Therefore, there is a shift to lands suitable for agriculture [8].

In the foothills of Boysun and Qurama mountain ranges, sorghum farming has been practiced since ancient times. In these areas, farming using spring and pond water also began to take shape[9].

O. Boriev notes the following about the traditional occupations and lifestyle of the inhabitants of the region: "In the 9th-10th centuries, the settled inhabitants of north-western Tokharistan (now the Surkhan oasis) were engaged in agriculture, handicrafts and trade. During this period, the masses of the people lived peacefully in the Kashkadarya oasis, and crafts and trade developed. In the developed middle ages, agriculture and animal husbandry developed traditionally in the oasis. In Lower Kashkadarya, on the contrary, conditional irrigation farming based on flood waters was practiced in relatively small areas[10]".

B. Kh. Karmisheva noted in her monograph that in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, the Dashti Kipchak Uzbeks settled in this region due to the favorable natural conditions for nomadism and cattle breeding in this part of Eastern Bukhara. It comes to the conclusion that being in a dominant position over the settled population for many centuries, the gradual transition of the next generations to farming, semi-sedentary and settled lifestyles is not due to the fact that they forgot the clan-tribe order and assimilated into the settled population, but because some settled groups joined them. [11].

In the monograph "Formation of the Uzbek people" by K.Sh.Shoniozov, it is noted that in the 9th-10th centuries, the Qarluqs were a large people, some of them engaged in animal husbandry, some in hunting, and some settled in farming.

In the work, it is also said that the Arabs who lived scattered in the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions in the 14th - 15th centuries were semi-sedentary and engaged in farming along with cattle breeding.

"Nekotorye voprosy etnicheskoy dynamics i etnicheskikh svyazey Uzbeks v XIV - XVII centuries." in his article, K.Sh.Shoniozov under the leadership of Shaibanikhan states that before the arrival of the Uzbek tribes in the Movarounnahr, Khorezm and Tashkent valleys, settled, semi-settled and nomadic people lived in these areas[12].

In N.Tursunov's researches, the information about the unique economic life of the people of Southern Surkhan is erased. He noted that the main occupations of the local population in the late 19th and early 20th centuries were agriculture, animal husbandry and handicrafts. At that time, according to its natural-geographical location, Surkhan Valley mainly owned irrigated, dryland and pasture lands, and the population made good use of all lands. In addition, it provides information about agriculture, animal husbandry, handicraft products and tools of the population [13].

Ethnographer and scientist N.Tursunov divides ethnic groups living in Surkhondarya into three regions according to economic characteristics:

First, ethnic groups such as Qarluq, Chigatai, Dorman, partly Kunhirat and Yuz were engaged in irrigated agriculture in the oasis of Sherobodarya, in the middle of Surkhandarya;

In the second region, the mountaineers-Katagons, Chigatoys, Garluks and mountain Tajiks living mainly in the mountain and sub-mountain areas engaged in gardening, cattle breeding and agriculture;

In the third region, ethnic groups engaged in animal husbandry - such as Kungyrot, Yuz, Dorman - were engaged in animal husbandry in the steppe zones between Sherobodarya, in the foothills of Bobotog, in the deserts of Kyzyriq, Bandikhon, Muzrobod, and Khayrabad, and in the highlands, they were engaged in dry farming.

The researcher comes to the appropriate conclusion that in the end of the 19th century - the beginning of the 20th century, in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis, like in other regions of Uzbekistan, two types of agriculture - irrigated agriculture in the oasis and steppe pasture cattle breeding - complemented each other and became harmonious.

At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, the clan-tribe division was kept stable among the semi-nomadic population in the southern regions. The main occupation of the semi-nomadic population is pastoralism, and in the Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya oasis, the semi-nomadic Uzbeks lived in deserts and semi-deserts, foothills and mountain plains.

The clan-tribe associations living in the south were divided into settled and semi-settled depending on the way of life and economy. The semi-sedentary population was mainly engaged in pasture cattle breeding, as their habitats were steppes (Koson, Chirakchi, Qamashi, Sherabad districts), mountains and mountain slopes (Shahrisabz, Kitab, Sariosia districts), and partially irrigated agriculture.

At the beginning of the 20th century, the population of these regions lived in patriarchal - seed farming conditions. During this period, the archaic way of life covered many aspects of economic activity, life and spiritual life of the population.

Patriarchal - seed farming lifestyle was preserved in the form of remnants of patronymics in the settled and semi-settled community engaged in farming, in the craft guilds of the cities and the neighborhood community, as well as in some ethnic groups of Uzbeks.

Livestock was considered one of the main means of production in large family estates in the southern regions. Sheep breeding was considered the main type of animal husbandry. At the beginning of the last century, in the south of Uzbekistan, sheep breeding was practiced mainly in the steppes and foothills. Karakol is raised in the Karshi zone, and Hisar sheep are raised in the Surkhan-Sherabad oasis. Horse breeding and racing horses were widely practiced in the desert and steppe areas. In farms, mainly women worked with cattle, and men with sheep farming.

Information about the occupations of the residents of the southern regions can also be obtained through various archival documents. In the information of the National Archives of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there is information about the traditional economy of the population living in Karshi uezd[14].

In addition, V.A.Polozov's articles provide information on the traditions of collective land use in southern oases[15], and D.Basov's article provides information about the traditional paykal system in the Sherabad oasis[16].

In I. Khidoyatov's article on the formation of the population of the southern regions of Uzbekistan, the Uzbeks living in the southern oases are divided into two groups, i.e. - descendants of ancient settled farmers and descendants of semi-nomadic inhabitants who have preserved the clan-tribe order. It is noted that the population belonging to the second group is the majority in this area[17].

In the 2nd volume of ethnographic essays in the column "Peoples of the World" published in 1963, it was noted that the main occupation of the Arabs who lived in the southern regions of Uzbekistan and Tajikistan in the 60s of the 20th century was cattle breeding and farming. In the steppe and desert regions where they live, animal husbandry has developed, while agriculture has developed in oases. Therefore, the local population called a variety of Karakol sheep "Arabian" or "Arabian". Arabs

who live in the southern regions of Uzbekistan and Tajikistan also breed hisori (humped) sheep [18].

Arabs have mastered cotton farming as well as cattle breeding. It is known that the Arabs have been engaged in leather processing and carpet weaving since ancient times [19], but there is hardly any information about their involvement in cotton growing in these sources. From this it can be concluded that they learned cotton cultivation from local peoples.

In the book titled "Uzbeki" published in 2011 in the column "Narody i kultura", the inhabitants of the southern regions of Uzbekistan at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century raised Karakul and humped sheep, goats, jaidari cattle, Lokai and Arabian horses, and one- and two-humped camels. the information about their activities is presented [20].

In his monograph on the history of Arabs in Uzbekistan, historian R.A.Rajabov writes, "Some Arabs were nomads and semi-nomads who moved around Termiz and Karshi. Most of the Arabs are farmers. "They have horses that graze in the deserts, which are a source of supply for the famous barra skins that are important in the trade," he says. Along with agriculture, cattle breeding has also developed[21].

In conclusion, in almost all the literature related to the research period, it is stated that people have been living in the southern regions since ancient times, irrigated agriculture in the areas near water bodies, rivers and springs, dry farming in mountain and sub-mountain regions, as well as types of animal husbandry such as sheep farming, cattle breeding, steppe and there is information about the existence of partial camel breeding in semi-desert areas. It should be noted that today's training of the southern regions continues the economic traditions of the past.

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